

ISSUES OF YOUTH COMPETENCE DEVELOPMENT BASED ON FAMILY AND SCHOOL PARTNERSHIP

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ANNOTATION

Communicative competence is a complex communicative skill and type of activity, which includes new social skills, communication norms and restrictions, knowledge, customs, etiquette, manners, educational orientations.

Keywords: Competence, Knowledge, important, information, students, social, situation, skill, communication, situation,

In fact, the concept of competence entered the field of education as a result of the scientific research of psychologists. From a psychological point of view, competence means "how a specialist behaves in unconventional situations, unexpected situations, communicates, takes a new way in relations with opponents, performs ambiguous tasks, uses information full of conflicts, and has a plan of movement in complex processes." Also, competences require constant enrichment of knowledge, learning of new information, understanding of important social requirements, ability to search for new information, process it and apply it in one's work. It is considered a real, formed personal quality based on knowledge, and it is an intellectual and personally determined social and professional formation of a person. Also, it includes a set of interrelated characteristics (knowledge, skills, methods of activity) identified in connection with specific objects and processes and necessary for high-quality production activity in relation to them. Therefore, there is a separate, special requirement for students regarding their preparation in the educational process.

Communicative competence is a complex communicative skill and type of activity, which includes new social skills, communication norms and restrictions, knowledge, customs, etiquette, manners, educational orientations. According to research scientist N. Amirov, "the ability to communicate effectively, which we call today communicative competence, has always been of interest to many scientists." In the fields of sociology, social psychology, pedagogy, and other modern fields of knowledge, attention is focused on the theoretical study of interpersonal relationships, communicative behavior of the individual. Even now, there is a social need to increase the number of research works in the training of personnel, aimed at preparing them for effective communication from the time of school and increasing their knowledge about the culture of communication. For this, the importance of scientific recommendations that can

be taken into account in the implementation of various educational reforms, in particular, in the transition of the education system to new state standards and in the training of future specialists, is growing. The main goal in the modern educational process is to organize effective continuous education aimed at developing students' personal abilities, scientific potential, knowledge, skills and qualifications. So, communicative competence is a general communicative characteristic of a person, which includes communication skills, knowledge, skills and social experience.

In the organization of pedagogical communication, it is not possible to proceed only from pedagogical goals and tasks, in fact, it is natural that they are the basis of the activity. The nature of communication in such a situation leads to the fact that the teacher always tries to communicate with him by expressing his opinion, that is, only "his" demand. In communicating with children, it is important to communicate with children, not by expressing "one's own" demands, but by taking into account their interests and aspirations, so that the child is within the radius of pedagogical goals with his own interest and his own world.

The basis of communicative competence is formed by:

- communication organization — interpersonal communication skills;
- maintaining communication, contact, establishing feedback;
- analysis of communication results.

Communication skills include:

- to give a socio-psychological forecast of the communicative situation in which it is necessary to communicate;
- socio-psychological programming of the communication process, based on the uniqueness of the communicative situation;
- implementation of socio-psychological management of communication processes in a communicative situation.

A competent approach to education envisages teaching students to effectively use the competences formed in various situations in personal, professional and social life. Special attention is paid to the ability to use relevant knowledge, skills, and abilities when facing unexpected, uncertain, new, problematic situations. Therefore, in the process of teaching each subject, competences related to it are formed based on its content and characteristics. Professor A. Abdukadirov emphasizes the problem of formation and development of a competent approach in students, that the development of competence is a process that does not stop throughout a person's life. In the

researches of our pedagogic scientists, the specific aspects of professional and pedagogic competence have been highlighted. For example, in his research, N.A. Muslimov cited communicative competence in the form of six qualities:

1) Motivational qualities (covers the needs, motives and goals for the chosen profession, which are formed and developed throughout a person's life);

2) Intellectual potential (on the basis of all official documents, the teacher strives to transfer information and data, to form knowledge, skills and qualifications);

3) Volitional qualities (striving for the goal, overcoming internal and external obstacles, physical and mental stress, self-control and initiative qualities);

4) Practical skills (psychological, pedagogical, methodical and technical-technological abilities, actions, skills of an individual in various spheres of activity and communication);

5) Emotional qualities (formation of the necessary skills to manage one's emotions (anger, anxiety, resentment, jealousy, sympathy, shame, pride, fear, happiness, love, etc.) and understand one's emotional states and their causes);

6) Self-control (freedom in choosing goals and means of achieving them, conscientiousness, critical approach to one's activities, comprehensiveness and understanding of actions, comparing one's own behavior with that of others, confidence in the future, maintaining and managing one's physical and psychological condition at the required level receive). Various definitions of competence are given in the psychological and pedagogical literature: Communicative competence is a system necessary for internal resources, effective communicative construction and actions within a certain framework of interpersonal relationships. Therefore, it means the level of interpersonal experience formation, that is, communication skills and the capacity to establish active relationships.

Conclusion: Family and neighborhood have a great role in the development of students' communicative competence. Students take the first step in the family and are brought up. Therefore, he will be influenced by his loved ones and will develop.

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